

Charles E. Fuller Theological Seminary

Exegetical Paper of
Psalm 110

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Psalm 110: A Royal Psalm

Introduction

Psalm 110 is the most often quoted of psalms in the New Testament and speaks of the Lord as King (vv1-3), as Priest (v.4), and as Warrior (vv. 5-7).¹ The unique communication between the LORD and God's anointed, as 'my Lord' is remarkable. (v1.) Could this be evidence of the Trinity as brought out by Jesus in Mark 12:35-37 and others in Hebrews 1:13 and Acts 2:34, where the Lord God promises to make a footstool to the enemies of God's anointed priest and king?

From a literary standpoint, this paper will evaluate the psalm's genre, dating, and context by viewing Psalm 110 as Jewish scripture before it was adapted so strongly by Christian apologists. The paper will explore the Hebrew of some key words and each verse of the psalm as explained by commentators.

Literary Analysis

Theme

Most scholars see the genre of Psalm 110 as a coronation of a royal figure.² W.P. Brown wrote, "The psalm is widely recognized as royal liturgy of some sort, at the very least a form of public utterance addressed to a royal figure."³ The theme of the psalm seems to center around verse one and five, both of which share the idea of the right hand of God. The introduction of the psalm begins with the curious phrase, "The Lord said to

¹ Charles C. Ryrie, *The Ryrie Study Bible*, (Chicago: Moody Press, 1978), 905.

² Brown, W. P. "A Royal Performance: Critical Notes on Psalm 110:3agamma-B." *Journal of Biblical Literature* 117, no. 1 (1998): 93.

³ Ibid.

my lord: ‘Sit at My right hand, until I make thine enemies a footstool for thy feet.’”⁴ Sitting at the right hand of God is a prophecy of power and victory for this king, spoken by God to the king. The right hand is symbolic of honor and authority.⁵ Because God’s authority and power are in the right hand of the king, he can defeat his enemies and experience victory, honor, and the refreshment of peace.⁶ The overarching theme is the power and authority of God as the true agent of victory over the foreign powers oppressing Israel.⁷ Some of the issues and questions to be addressed by this paper include the following:

- 1) The issue of the identity of the recipient of Yahweh, in verse one, is a serious question and was picked up in Mark 12:36, Matt 22:44, and Luke 20:42 as well as Heb 1:13.
- 2) What is the significance of the rod or scepter in verse 2?
- 3) What does the *womb of the morning and dew of thy youth* mean in verse three?
- 4) Should the word מְלִכֵי־צֶדֶק (Ps. 110:4 WTT) be read as a proper name or as a designation of an office of justice?⁸
- 5) Who is the subject in vv. 5-7 and is Adonai used interchangeably with Yahweh?
- 6) What is the dating of this psalm?
- 7) How did the Jewish and Christian communities use Psalm 110 in their liturgy and theology?
- 8) How do those who view God as love understand and cope with the aspects of the text that speak of God as a warrior-king demolishing his enemies?

Structure

According to Frank Hossfeld and his team, the psalm can be divided into two main sections, the divine speech vv.1-3, and the divine oath vv. 4-7, with ten elements.

⁴ Psalm 110:1 NASB.

⁵ North, C.R. and George A. Buttrick, ed. *The Interpreter’s Dictionary of the Bible: R-Z*, (Nashville: Parthenon Press, Eleventh Printing, 1980), 79.

⁶ Longman, III, Tremper. *Psalms: An Introduction and Commentary*, (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 2014), 382. ProQuest Ebook Central

⁷ F. L. Hossfeld, & Eric Zenger, & K. Baltzer, & L. M. Maloney, *Psalms 3: A Commentary on Psalms 101-150* (Augsburg: Fortress Publishers, 2011), 154.

⁸ F. L. Hossfeld, 143.

- I. **I. The Divine Speech:** Throne Companionship with Yhwh
- II. 1 Quotation of the divine saying
- III. 2 Powerful rule from Zion
- IV. 3abc People in holy array
- V. 3de Dew of youth
- VI. **II. The Divine Oath:** Priest like Melchizedek
- VII. 4 Quotation of the divine oath
- VIII. 5 Yhwh at the right of the priest-king
- IX. 6 Judgment among the nations throughout the world
- X. 7 Yhwh's victory⁹
- XI.

Robert Alden suggests Psalm 110 has a chiasmic pattern when the Hebrew of verse 7 is repointed to read “the Bestower of the Succession set him on his throne” instead of the NASB, “He will lift up His head.” Alden drew a parallel to the Ugaritic word *drkt* which means *throne* and not *way*. If this is a correct translation it destroys an older chiasmic pattern between the *dew* and *brook* of verses 3 and 7.¹⁰ Alden wrote,

- A The LORD installs the king (verse 1)
- B His commission to conquer (verse 2)
- C The day of power (verse 3)
- D The LORD promises an oath (verse 4)
- C The day of wrath (verse 5)
- B He will conquer (verse 6)
- A The LORD installs the king (verse 7)¹¹

It is interesting to note that most scholars agree there are two sections to the psalm, with identifying speech from God at the beginning of each section and additional agreement between the chiasm of the two sections, being ABC and CBA.¹²

Genre

⁹ F. L. Hossfeld, 147.

¹⁰ Joyce M. Brooks, “An Exegetical Review of Psalm 110” (*Evangelical Theological Society*, 1990: 1-16), 3.

¹¹ *Ibid*, 2.

¹² *Ibid*, 4.

According to Bernhard Anderson, the genre of Psalm 110 is a royal psalm and is part of a trilogy of royal psalms including Psalm 108,109, and 110, as each is superscripted as, “A Psalm of David.”¹³

The social setting of the psalm is high praise of God for establishing a royal figure. The statements about the king that are originating from Yahweh may be part of temple worship in celebration of the victories accomplished by king David under the authority of Yahweh.¹⁴ All of the accomplishments of David should be seen as coming from the LORD.

The objects noted in section one include: right hand, footstool, feet, scepter, womb, and dew. The objects noted in section two include: right hand, kings, nations, corpses, chief men, country, brook, and head. This psalm could have been performed as a means of verbal reinforcement of the power given to the king as representative of the community, to destroy the enemies of the community, and to have dominion in perpetuity, something consistent with Davidic kingdom theology.

Point of view, characterization, style, mood, and selectivity

The most important characters of the psalm are Yahweh and the anointed one. Yahweh has given this unique person all the authority under heaven and has stretched out his kingdom emanating from Zion, the city of David. Enemies are mentioned as subjects to be destroyed by the king, (vv.1, 2) along with other characters as other kings to be shattered (v.5), nations to be judged (v.6a), corpses (v.6b), and heads of state to be crushed (v.6c). The central figure is both king and priest, as was Melchizedek. This kingdom will last forever because the Melchizedek priesthood is an everlasting

¹³ Bernhard W. Anderson, *Out of the Depths: Studies into the Meaning of the Book of Psalms*. (New York: Joint Commission on Education and Cultivation, Board of Missions, United Methodist Church, 1970), 223.

¹⁴ Ibid.

priesthood based on the oath of Yahweh. (v.4) The style is poetic in the English which uses the word “Thy or Thine” seven times in the first strophe, and the word "He" or "His" eight times, for Yahweh or the subject in the second strophe. The purpose of this psalm appears to emphasize the power of God as the source of the king’s mighty authority and dominion, as the second strophe delineates beginning at verse four.¹⁵ The point of view of Psalm 110 is hopeful, in the place of the Psalter, comes after Ps 89 that begins the fall of the Davidic monarchy, but carries the hope of restoration.¹⁶

Dating and Origin

J. Brooks reports that if Psalm 110 is an enthronement hymn then it is probably pre-exilic. Other scholars see it during the Maccabean-Hasmonean period citing the priest-king of Simon (143–135 b.c.e.) Still other scholars see the dating as the (early) postexilic expectation of a restoration of Israel as a likely candidate.¹⁷ According to Walter Brueggemann, "The psalm likely comes from Jerusalem and the time of the Davidic monarchy."¹⁸

Verse-by-Verse Commentary

PSALM 110

A Psalm of David

-I-

THE LORD says to my lord:

"Sit at my right hand,
until I make thine enemies
a footstool for thy feet."

(Ps 110:1 NASB)

¹⁵ Joyce M. Brooks, “An Exegetical Review of Psalm 110” (*Evangelical Theological Society*, 1990: 1-16), 9.

¹⁶ Brueggemann, Walter, and W. H Bellinger. *Psalms*. New Cambridge Bible Commentary. (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 479.

¹⁷ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 144.

¹⁸ Brueggemann, 479.

Some Jewish scholars see David speaking about Yahweh who is speaking to a king, however David as witness of this event, cannot be the subject and the observer. Other scholars see a person in the royal court speaking to a Davidic king in verses 1-3, and later speaking about or to Yahweh in verses 4-7.¹⁹ Frank L. Hossfeld and Eric Zenger regarded verse one as a historical connection to king David. Zenger wrote, The use of David is a link to the enthronement of the historical David or the Davidic kings, which is concretely described in the psalm as election by Yhwh and a promise of support.²⁰

The right hand language establishes the highest place of honor and authority for this Lord. To sit (yashab), also means to abide or dwell, is a figure of enthroning the individual or king with a permanent status. Yashab is translated "to enthrone" ten times in the OT.²¹

-II-

The LORD will stretch forth
Thy strong scepter
from Zion, *saying*,
"Rule in the midst
of Thine enemies."
(Ps 110:2 NASB)

The importance of the object and image of the word *matteh* in verse 2, which many English translations render as *scepter* is however translated 34 times as *staff*, and 24 times as *rod*, with 168 times as *tribe* or *tribes*.²² Translators may be using scepter because they see a strong connection to Gen 49:10 "*The scepter will not depart from Judah, nor the ruler's staff from between his feet, until he to whom it belongs shall come and the obedience of the nations shall be his.*" *Matteh* is also a symbol of strong headship as it is often used in the Hebrew Bible to connote assigned power from another for the purpose of ruling.²³ (2 Chr 5:2, Jos 1:1-2, Num 1:16, Gen 38:18) Hossfeld explains the

¹⁹ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 141.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ James Strong, Strong's Exhaustive Concordance of the Bible, (Peabody: Hendricksons, 2007), BibleWorks, v10.08: Word Analysis of "Yahshab," Strongs #3427.

²² <https://www.blueletterbible.org/lang/lexicon/lexicon.cfm?ot=KJV&page=4&strongs=H4294&t=NIV#lexresults>

²³ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 142.

Hebrew verb, םלש, is not a jussive or future tense but is meant to be present tense. He wrote,

"It is about the effective power of rule that begins with the ascent of the throne." ²⁴

-III-

Thy people will volunteer
Freely in the day of
Thy power;
In holy array, from the
womb of the dawn,
Thy youth are to Thee as
the dew.
(Ps 110:3 NASB)

Verse 3b and 3c have been particularly difficult Hebrew phrases for translators however W. P. Brown concludes,

The royal figure is commanded to go forth from the womb toward the dawn, suggesting perhaps a rite of passage in this royal liturgy pronounced by the oracle giver. What the womb and the dawn, as well as the dew, might signify in this snippet of royal liturgy invites some tantalizing possibilities that deserve further study.²⁵

Zenger looked at ancient readings of the text in the MT and Jerome for different vocalizations and meanings. He proposes a different reading of the text,

To me is the dignity
on the day of your power/birth.
On holy mountains,
out of the womb of the dawn
I bore/begot you as dew.²⁶

The Douay-Rheims Bible translation of A.D. 1772 offers a differing perspective on 3b,

From a womb before
the morning star I begot you.²⁷

Hossfeld thought the phrasing may have a military connection stating,

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ W. P. Brown "A Royal Performance: Critical Notes on Psalm 110:3agamma-B." (*Journal of Biblical Literature* 117, no. 1 (1998): 93-96), 96.

²⁶ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 142.

²⁷ Robert C. Hill, 210.

The intertextual references to Ps 29:2, Ps 96:9, and especially 1 Chr 16:29 with "thy people" being an army "in holy array."²⁸

-IV-

The LORD has sworn and
will not change His mind,
"Thou art a priest forever
According to the order of
Melchizedek."
(Ps 110:4 NASB)

The introduction and inclusion of the priesthood of Melchizedek in verse 4b presents a number of questions about the imagery and meaning for this royal pronouncement. It does seem implausible for it not to be a proper name but the inclusion does present a powerful combination of official roles and a unique kingdom on the level of Abraham's blessing by the ancient priestly monarch. (Gen 14:18) Here, Yahweh is swearing an oath to the Davidic Kingdom that it will last forever, in perpetuity.²⁹

-V-

The Lord is at Thy right hand;
He will shatter kings in
The day of His wrath.
(Ps 110:5 NASB)

Verse five repeats the image of verse one, "The Lord is at Thy right hand." The psalmist appears to want to make clear God is the one acting on behalf of the people to destroy the enemies and bring complete victory to pass by empowering their king.³⁰ However, Pierre Auffret believed the structural devices of verse 5 supports a reversal in the sentences, and the person who holds possession in the predicate exchange places, so that Yahweh is the subject of verse 5 and the king is the subject in the following five "He's" with the final He becoming Yahweh once again who lifts up the head of the king in verse 7.³¹ However, the noun is Adonai in verse 5a, not Yahweh, which may be the same subject being addressed in verse one. Adonai, the one doing all the actions on

²⁸ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 143.

²⁹ Elizabeth R. Hayes, Fuller Seminary Lecture on Video: "Week 8 Psalm 110", Published May 16, 2016.

³⁰ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 150.

³¹ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 143.

behalf of the subject, is at the right hand of subject b, "Thy". Perhaps the Psalmist uses Yahweh and Adonai interchangeably. However, Hossfeld believes the subject of the actions can only be Yahweh.³²

-VI-

He will judge among the nations,
He will fill them with corpses,
He will shatter the chief men
over a broad country.
(Ps 110:6 NASB)

Brueggemann explains verse 6 as the continuation of the king's victories and exploits by stating,

The divine ruler brings judgment by defeating and shattering nations "over the wide earth."³³

This proclamation is echoed by the vision of Isaiah to see to glory of God filling the whole earth. (Isa 60:1-2) Brueggemann continues,

Verses 5–6 bring to mind the historical tradition of the great victories YHWH brought the people in early Israel. YHWH gloriously defeated those who opposed the covenant people; in Psalm 110 YHWH promises such victories for the ruler of the covenant people.³⁴

-VII-

He will drink from the
brook by the wayside;
Therefore He will lift up
His head.
(Ps 110:7 NASB)

Verse 7 is another enigmatic verse similar to verse 3 but carries with it a sense of completion or rest after returning victoriously from the battles of war. The images evoke a contrast to the preceding verses of judgment, pursuit, and destruction. H. J. Kraus and C. C. Broyles relate the drinking from the stream to a coronation ritual of drinking

³² Ibid.

³³ Brueggemann, 480.

³⁴ Ibid.

renewing water from the spring of Gihon (1 Kgs 1:38) in Jerusalem.³⁵ Still others have reappointed the Hebrew to translate verse 7 as, "He will appoint you as Bestower of inheritance."³⁶ Either way, it is a fitting conclusion of peaceful triumph for the victor.

Jewish Use and Expectations

After the second temple the Jews developed a fervent expectation of the restoration of the Davidic kingdom and would have likely used this psalm to celebrate and anticipate a messianic fulfillment.³⁷ Brueggemann explains,

The Psalter was also brought together after the destruction of Jerusalem and the trauma of exile. Those realities suggest that the community understood Psalm 110 in terms of hopes for the restoration of the monarchy or at least some kind of hope that YHWH was not finished with the faith community of ancient Israel.³⁸

The inclusion of Yahweh, David, Zion, and Melchizedek provided the Jewish community in using this psalm a particularly powerful connection to Israel's history and harkens to various covenant promises for Yahweh to remain faithful.

Christian Views and Uses

Dealing with imprecatory psalms and psalms of war are not easily assimilated into Christian theology. However, Joyce Brooks wrote, "This warrior language is highly problematic for many who view Christ only as the Priestly Redeemer." She uncovers research that identifies the psalm as a victory psalm rather than a coronation psalm, showing that 5b is the Lord acting and not the king. However in verse 7 it is Yahweh who lifts up the head of the Lord.³⁹ Perhaps this is a picture of the resurrection.

The Sonship of Jesus was celebrated by the early church fathers as they commented on Psalm 110. Quentin F. Wesselschmidt summarized some of these theologians when he wrote,

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Joyce M. Brooks, "An Exegetical Review of Psalm 110" (*Evangelical Theological Society*, 1990: 1-16), 5.

³⁷ E. Zenger, F. L. Hossfeld, 144.

³⁸ Brueggemann, 480.

³⁹ Brooks, 9.

The Father's invitation to his Son to sit at his right hand is a sign of his love and esteem for his Son (Ambrose). Christ, who now sits at the Father's right hand, will come to award the just with eternal life and to mete out eternal punishment to the wicked (Nicetas). The descent of the Holy Spirit on the disciples at Pentecost was proof that Christ ascended and now sits at the Father's right hand (Maximu).⁴⁰

As Jesus debated the Pharisees regarding the identity of the Christ, he used Psalm 110 to teach them something beyond their thinking. Robert Hill wrote,

The Pharisees acknowledged that the Christ is son of David; but that the Lord was also from David they had no idea. So, without canceling what they acknowledged, he adds the missing link, teaching that he himself is both his son according to the flesh and his Lord as God and creator.⁴¹

Hossfeld's team of theologians reported on the reception of Psalm 110:1 in the NT,

The motif of sitting "at the right hand of God" is used frequently (cf. Mark 14:62 par.; 16:19; Acts 5:31; 7:55-56; Rom 8:34; Eph 1:20; Col 3:1; Heb 1:3; 8:1; 10:12; 12:2; 1 Pet 3:22) to present Jesus' divine sonship and his resurrection as a heavenly enthronement: "Jesus is integrated into the heavenly (throne)room of God and has a share in God's potential power shown in judgment and salvation."⁴²

Conclusion

Both Christians and Jewish communities have celebrated Psalm 110 as God's promise to triumph over the enemies of God. The relationship of the people to this kingdom that proceeds in perpetuity is free and not forced, (v.3) implying a loving relationship between God and His people. Psalm 110 stands out as the premiere evidence of messianic prophecy of the second person of the trinity because of Mark 12:36 and Heb 1:13. Christians should view this Psalm with great joy as they ponder the majesty of Jesus Christ who has ascended to the right hand of God, (v.1, 5) who now rules (v.2) and will come again to rule over his kingdom, with all of the elect who will constantly be renewed in the power of God, (v.3) a kingdom that will spread like the glory of God over the whole earth. (v.6)

⁴⁰ Quentin F. Wesselschmidt, ed. *Psalms 51-150*, (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 2002), 261.

⁴¹ Robert C. Hill. *Theodoret of Cyrus: Commentary on the Psalms, 73-150*. (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2001), 201 *eBook Academic Collection (EBSCOhost)*, EBSCOhost (accessed April 13, 2018).

⁴² Erich Zenger, & F. L. Hossfeld, 153.

King David must have understood Yahweh was the rightful ruler over Israel, that it was evil for the people to demand a human king when they forced Samuel to anoint Saul as King. (1Sam 10:19) Perhaps David wrote this Psalm to give Yahweh the proper honor as the One giving victory to Israel, as was historically the case. (Num 21:21-35) Regardless, it gave hope to Israel during the post-exilic years for the restoration of the Davidic reign.⁴³

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⁴³ Erich Zenger, & F. L. Hossfeld, 154.

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